

DMP Climate Neutrality Decision Models in Action

Version 4

Description

DMP for National Research Program project "Climate Neutrality Decision Models in Action"

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

VPP-KEM-
Klimatneitralitate-2023/1-0002
(VPP-KEM-
Klimatneitralitāte-2023/1-0002)

Researchers

Ieva Pakere (orcid:0000-0001-8069-4484)

Organizations

University of Latvia, Riga Technical University, Riga Stradiņš
University, VIDZEMES AUGSTSKOLA

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP Climate Neutrality Decision Models in Action

Description:

DMP for National Research Program project "Climate Neutrality Decision Models in Action"

Researchers:

Ieva Pakere (orcid:0000-0001-8069-4484)

Organizations:

University of Latvia

Riga Technical University

Riga Stradiņš University

VIDZEMES AUGSTSKOLA

Contact: Kalnbalkīte Antra (antra.kalnbalkite@rtu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: VPP-KEM-Klimatneitralitate-2023/1-0002 (VPP-KEM-Klimatneitralitāte-2023/1-0002)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-06-05

4. Templates

Descriptions

D4.3. List of requirements for model data quality

Deliverable D4.3 outlines model quality requirements for greenhouse gas emission modelling. It is part of the Latvian State Research Programme “Climate Neutrality” (Project No. VPP-KEM-Klimata neitralitāte-2023/1-0002) and supports the development of the CLIMA-SIM-LV uncertainty and scenario modelling framework.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The document provides a structured analysis of input data (Activity Data – AD), emission factors (EF), Tier methodologies, and associated uncertainties relevant to greenhouse gas (GHG) emission modelling.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1000

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The aggregated data is not available

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18853969>

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any software able to open data file

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The costs are covered by the project funding.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

D.4.1 List of tools and instruments for potential application

CLIMA-SIM-LV

To analyse the different possible pathways towards climate neutrality, a variety of advanced modelling tools and instruments are used to simulate and analyse the impacts of policies and measures on energy systems, emissions, land use and the economy. These tools and instruments provide a comprehensive view, integrating economic, demographic and environmental data, thus offering future scenarios and the ability to assess the effectiveness of different strategies. The set of modelling tools and instruments selected for potential application in the CLIMA SIM-LV is a diverse range of sophisticated tools designed to address different aspects of environmental policy analysis.

A compilation of these tools is provided in the form of a list.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data is to list the modelling tools and instruments selected for potential application in the CLIMA SIM-LV model.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Aggregate data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

PDF

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1000

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

The aggregated data is not available

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14824452>

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any software able to open data file

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The costs are covered by the project funding.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Antra Kalnbalķīte (orcid: [0000-0001-5904-580X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5904-580X))
- Anna Kubule (0000-0002-0518-3163)
- Ieva Pakere (orcid: [0000-0001-8069-4484](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8069-4484))

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Supplementary data for article "DATA ACQUISITION FOR THE RENOVATION OF THE 20ST CENTURY HOUSING STOCK OF LATVIA. APPROACHING CLIMATE NEUTRALITY"

Indicator values for energy sector (years 2015-2023). Data collected from different data sources.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

Supplementary data for article "DATA ACQUISITION FOR THE RENOVATION OF THE 20ST CENTURY HOUSING STOCK OF LATVIA. APPROACHING CLIMATE NEUTRALITY"

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Administrative records data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

200

KB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

Yes, we have considered and might re-use the data but at this point it is not clear when and how exactly.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Students, Researchers

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Any which accepts CSV, e.g. Excel

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Andris Lapans (0000-0002-7247-5537)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

The nature of the data does not require elevated protection

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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